

Standard Transfer Metadata for Born Digital Transfers

Born digital transfers

- Public Records Act 2005 – government agencies to transfer records in ANY form
- Urgent digital transfers accepted from 2006 - no means of processing or actively preserving them, just secure storage
- 2010-2013 Government Digital Archive Programme (GDAP), aimed to deliver:
 - new digital preservation system ✓
 - ability to process digital transfers ✗

Transfer requirements

- GDAP closed early but the need for transfer process ability did not disappear
- Built minimal requirement workflow and process (python scripts, guidelines, etc.) > first "official" transfer in 2015 and all subsequent transfers
- Requirements for agencies were simple (we thought), had to change to bare minimum over time
 - transfer files "as they are" in any format; do not migrate formats before transfer
 - metadata in machine-readable form (ideally CSV), all the metadata fields

Every transfer is a project

- Lack of metadata standard is an issue
 - field naming inconsistencies
 - content issues
 - format and encoding quirks
- For each transfer we need to:
 - analyse the metadata fields
 - map them to fields used in our archival description system

STMf

Standard Transfer Metadata File

- Prescribing how the metadata for born-digital transfers must look
- XSD and spreadsheet template + detailed guidelines
- Agencies will use those to export metadata from their systems (vendor cooperation will be needed)
- Export templates already exist in some EDRMS, e.g. NAA (National Archives of Australia), VEO (Victoria, Australia), etc.
- We plan to provide supplementary tools like an STMf validator

STMf structure

- Header – details about the transfer
- Item – item/records descriptive and technical metadata
- ItemRelationships – between items, relationship types

